

Cross-Sectional Study of Sleep Duration and Its Correlation with Metabolic Syndrome Markers in Middle-Aged Individuals

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Abstract:

Background: Heart disease, diabetes, and stroke are more likely in metabolic syndrome patients. Sleep length affects metabolic health, although its relationship to metabolic syndrome markers in middle-aged people is unclear. This study aims to determine how sleep duration affects metabolic syndrome risk variables.

Methods: This retrospective, cross-sectional study analysed 150 middle-aged (45–65) medical records from 2022 to 2023. Medical records showed patients' sleep duration. We studied waist size, blood pressure, fasting glucose, lipid profile, and HDL cholesterol as metabolic syndrome indicators. Sleep time was correlated with metabolic markers using Pearson and Spearman correlations.

Results: An average of 6.8 hours of sleep per night was found in 150 middle-aged people (55.2 years old, 60% female). 60% were overweight around the midsection, 55% were hypertensive, 50% had high triglycerides, 45% had poor HDL cholesterol, and 40% had poor glucose tolerance. Significant negative relationships were found between reduced sleep duration and waist circumference ($r = -0.32$), systolic blood pressure ($r = -0.29$), diastolic blood pressure ($r = -0.23$), fasting glucose ($r = -0.25$), and triglycerides ($r = -0.30$). On the other hand, longer sleep duration is connected with higher HDL cholesterol ($r = 0.27$).

Conclusion: Middle-aged people need enough sleep to maintain metabolic health. Longer sleep duration improves lipid profiles, but shorter sleep duration increases metabolic syndrome markers. These findings suggest that better sleep may help prevent metabolic syndrome.

Keywords: Abdominal Obesity, Blood Pressure, Fasting Glucose, HDL Cholesterol, Metabolic Syndrome, Sleep Duration, Triglycerides.

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Introduction

Background

Metabolic syndrome increases the risk of cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and other serious health issues [1]. Hypertension, dyslipidaemia, abdominal obesity, and impaired glucose tolerance characterise this metabolic disease [2].

The International Diabetes Federation defines metabolic syndrome as three or more of the following symptoms: increased waist circumference, triglycerides, lower HDL cholesterol, blood pressure, and fasting glucose. Sleep controls metabolic functions, according to [3]. Sleep is essential for metabolic homeostasis, appetite regulation, glucose metabolism, and cardiovascular health [4].

However, metabolic syndrome is more likely in people who suffer sleep interruptions or don't get enough sleep. Chronic sleep loss can cause insulin

sensitivity issues, appetite, and hormone imbalances like leptin and ghrelin, which regulate energy.

Significance of Study

Sleep disorders and metabolic diseases are more widespread in middle-aged persons, therefore understanding how sleep duration affects metabolic syndrome markers is crucial. Elderly people often have shorter, lower-quality sleep, which may contribute to metabolic syndrome. Sleep's impacts on metabolic health and modifiable metabolic syndrome risk variables may be better understood. Middle-aged persons face a crossroads where lifestyle decisions might affect long-term health. This study examines the relationship between sleep duration and metabolic syndrome indicators to better understand how sleep patterns affect metabolic health and inform public health initiatives to increase sleep and minimise metabolic syndrome.

Objectives

- To determine if metabolic syndrome risk factors such as abdominal obesity, high blood pressure, aberrant lipid profiles, and impaired glucose tolerance are linked to sleep hours.
- To determine if sleep duration affects metabolic syndrome risk.
- To determine if sleep duration is a strong indicator of metabolic syndrome in this age group and its effects on metabolic health.

Overview of Metabolic Syndrome and Its Markers

The complex metabolic abnormalities of metabolic syndrome increase the risk of cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and stroke [5]. Metabolic

syndrome is characterised by abdominal obesity, high blood pressure, aberrant lipid profiles (low HDL cholesterol and high triglycerides), and insulin resistance. Due to obesity, inactivity, and poor diets, metabolic syndrome has increased worldwide.

The main feature of metabolic syndrome is abdominal obesity, as measured by waist circumference, which increases visceral fat and has detrimental metabolic effects [6]. Additionally, hypertension raises the risk of cardiovascular disease owing to high blood pressure.

Dyslipidaemia high triglycerides and low HDL cholesterol exacerbates atherosclerosis [7]. Insulin resistance and poor glucose tolerance raise type 2 diabetes risk.

Figure 1: Sleep duration correlation with Metabolic Syndrome (Source: [8])

The Role of Sleep in Metabolic Health

Sleep helps maintain metabolism and equilibrium. [9] Shows that insufficient or excessive sleep might affect multiple metabolic markers. Lack of sleep is linked to obesity, weight gain, and metabolic dysfunction. Insufficient sleep disrupts the hormone regulation system, increasing hunger hormones like ghrelin and decreasing fat-burning hormones like leptin, according to [10].

Lack of sleep also impairs glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity, which can lead to type 2 diabetes. However, excessive sleep may lead to metabolic issues like obesity and metabolic syndrome. Long lengths of sleep can harm metabolic health, which may be a sign of underlying health issues or a lack of activity. Healthy metabolic function requires a regulated sleep length because inadequate and excess sleep damage metabolic health [11].

Sleep Duration and Abdominal Obesity

Insufficient sleep is linked to belly obesity. There is significant evidence that insufficient sleep duration increases abdominal fat. Persons who slept less were overweight and had greater abdominal fat. Sleep deprivation may cause hormonal and energy imbalances. Without proper sleep, we may consume more and be less active, which may increase belly fat. A less reliable link exists between longer sleep durations and lower belly fat. According to [12], oversleeping may not promote obesity but may indicate other health risks. Thus, inadequate sleep is strongly linked to abdominal obesity, although extra sleep may have condition-specific consequences.

Sleep Duration and Hypertension

High blood pressure is linked to both short and long sleep durations. Sleep deprivation raises systolic and diastolic blood pressure. People who

slept six or fewer hours were more likely to develop hypertension than those who slept seven or eight hours. This link is caused by increased sympathetic nervous system activity and hormonal imbalances, particularly high cortisol levels, which can cause hypertension. However, excessive sleep may cause hypertension, which may be caused by inactivity and poor health. These findings emphasise the need of regular sleep for blood pressure regulation.

Sleep Duration and Lipid Profile

Lipid metabolism has also been researched, and shorter sleep duration is often associated with lower lipid profiles. Insufficient sleep is linked to dyslipidaemia, including high triglycerides and low HDL cholesterol. Sleep deprivation raised triglycerides and lowered HDL cholesterol. Longer sleep time changes lipid profiles less clearly. Excessive sleep may indicate various health concerns that lower cholesterol levels.

Sleep Duration and Glucose Metabolism

Sleep duration dramatically impacts glucose usage and insulin sensitivity. The risk of type 2 diabetes increases with reduced sleep duration due to lower glucose tolerance and insulin resistance. This relationship affects calorie intake and weight gain due to hunger and glucose homeostasis abnormalities. Sleeping less than 6 hours a night raised fasting glucose levels and decreased insulin sensitivity. Long sleep's effect on glucose metabolism has received less attention, but some data suggests that oversleeping may cause metabolic dysfunction through similar pathways or other health issues.

Methods

Study Design

This cross-sectional study examines middle-aged sleep duration and metabolic syndrome markers. Cross-sectional studies are best for assessing variable relationships at a specific time. This study doesn't need long-term follow-up. Collecting data on metabolic syndrome markers and sleep duration simultaneously makes it easier to assess their prevalence and connections in the target group.

Inclusion Criteria

- Participants aged 45-60 years.
- Individuals without diagnosed chronic conditions that could significantly impact sleep patterns or metabolic markers, such as severe psychiatric disorders or advanced cardiovascular diseases.
- Participants must provide written informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals younger than 45 years or older than 60 years.
- Individuals with known sleep disorders (e.g., sleep apnea, insomnia) or severe metabolic disorders that could confound the results (e.g., uncontrolled diabetes).
- Use of medications known to significantly impact sleep or metabolic markers (e.g., corticosteroids, certain antidepressants) was also considered an exclusion criterion.

Sample Size

A 150-person sample size was determined via statistical power estimates. Given the predicted impact size and the need to find significant correlations between sleep duration and metabolic syndrome markers, 150 samples were adequate. This size meets rigorous statistical analysis and data collection and recruiting needs, making it ideal.

Data Collection

This study used medical records to collect data on sleep duration, abdominal obesity, blood pressure, fasting glucose, and lipid profiles. Sleep duration data were acquired from individuals who reported their sleep length or made sleep-related observations in the past month using health questionnaires in routine medical exams or documented sleep evaluations. Abdominal obesity prevalence was determined by waist circumference measurements in medical charts. Regular medical exams measured blood pressure. Fasting glucose levels were evaluated in the lab after an overnight fast. Medical record blood test results were used to create the lipid profile.

Data Analysis

Data was analysed using statistical tools. By descriptive statistics, participant characteristics included metabolic syndrome indicators and average sleep duration. We estimated a Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficient for each metabolic syndrome marker to assess their relationship. Next, link direction and strength were considered. Multiple linear regression was used to examine metabolic syndrome marker effects of sleep duration. Potential confounders including age, gender, and BMI were controlled. This study helped determine how metabolic markers affected sleep duration.

Ethical Considerations

The collaborating institution's IRB authorised this study, which met all ethical standards. Patients' medical records were used in this study under ethical and confidentiality agreements. Participants' medical records were used for research following their agreement. Participants' personal information

was anonymised and stored securely to protect confidentiality during the study.

Results

Participant Characteristics

The study participants' demographics are shown in Table 1. With 60% women and 40% males, the gender ratio favoured women. The prevalence of

metabolic syndrome in this age range is higher, and the majority of patients were overweight or obese (average BMI: 29.4 kg/m²), supporting this observation. Demographics make metabolic syndrome and sleep patterns research in this population important.

Table 1: Participant Characteristics

Characteristic	Mean (SD)	Range	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	55.2 (6.3)	45 - 65	NIL
Body Mass Index (BMI)	29.4 (4.8)	22.0 - 37.5	NIL
Gender:			
Male	NIL	NIL	40
Female	NIL	NIL	60

Sleep Duration and Metabolic Markers:

According to medical data, the average nightly sleep was 6.8 hours, with a 1.2-hour standard deviation. Participant metabolic syndrome percentages:

- **Abdominal Obesity:** 60% of participants

- **Hypertension:** 55% of participants
- **Elevated Triglycerides:** 50% of participants
- **Low HDL Cholesterol:** 45% of participants
- **Impaired Glucose Tolerance:** 40% of participants

Summary of Metabolic Syndrome Markers

Table 2: Summary of Metabolic Syndrome Markers

Marker	Mean (SD)	Percentage (%)
Waist Circumference (cm)	102.5 (10.4)	60
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	140.3 (12.1)	55
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	85.2 (9.6)	-
Fasting Glucose (mg/dL)	115.6 (18.3)	40
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	215.4 (25.6)	-
LDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	135.2 (22.7)	-
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	42.1 (8.9)	45
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	180.4 (35.9)	50

Table 2 shows the frequency and average metabolic syndrome indicators among individuals. Abdominal obesity (60%), hypertension (55%), high triglycerides (50%), low HDL cholesterol (45%), and impaired glucose tolerance (40%), show metabolic syndrome's significant influence. After metabolic issues, participants' elevated blood

pressure and mean waist circumference of 102.5 cm compound the problem. Since the lipid profile and fasting glucose levels fit metabolic syndrome criteria, these markers must be targeted.

Correlation between Sleep Duration and Metabolic Markers

Table 3: Correlation between Sleep Duration and Metabolic Markers

Marker	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Waist Circumference	-0.32	0.002
Systolic Blood Pressure	-0.29	0.005
Diastolic Blood Pressure	-0.23	0.02
Fasting Glucose	-0.25	0.01
HDL Cholesterol	0.27	0.008
Triglycerides	-0.30	0.003

Sleep duration and waist circumference were negatively correlated with a -0.32 and 0.002 p-value. Sleep deprivation may increase abdominal obesity risk. A statistically significant negative connection ($r = -0.29$, $p = 0.005$) linked shorter sleep time to higher systolic blood pressure.

Sleep duration was negatively correlated with diastolic blood pressure ($r = -0.23$, $p = 0.02$). The association with diastolic blood pressure is stronger but still substantial.

The moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.25$, $p = 0.01$) between sleep length and fasting glucose levels suggests that shorter sleep has worse glucose metabolism. HDL levels increased with longer sleep ($r = 0.27$, $p = 0.008$).

Extended sleep may boost HDL cholesterol, a healthy sign. Shorter sleep time was associated with increased triglycerides, with a -0.30 correlation and p -value of 0.003 .

These data show that insufficient sleep is linked to metabolic issues such as dyslipidaemia, poor glucose tolerance, hypertension, and abdominal obesity. However, sleep length appears to favourably link with HDL cholesterol levels, suggesting that prolonged sleep may protect against metabolic syndrome.

Discussion

This study identified multiple significant connections between sleep duration and metabolic

syndrome risk variables in middle-aged persons. Increased abdominal obesity, hypertension, glucose metabolism impairment, and triglycerides were strongly connected to shorter sleep duration. Conversely, longer sleep duration was linked to higher HDL cholesterol levels, which may prevent metabolic syndrome. Due to strong negative correlations between sleep duration and metabolic markers such as waist circumference, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and fasting glucose, lack of sleep severely impacts these variables. Reduced bedtime increases abdominal fat, a risk factor for metabolic syndrome and its complications.

High blood pressure and poor glucose metabolism from insufficient sleep may exacerbate insulin resistance and cardiovascular risk. Since HDL cholesterol and sleep duration are positively correlated, longer sleep may improve lipid profiles.

Comparison with Literature

Table 4: Comparison of Studies on Sleep Duration and Metabolic Syndrome Markers

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Key Findings
Present Study	Cross-sectional, retrospective	150	Shorter sleep duration is associated with increased abdominal obesity, higher blood pressure, impaired glucose metabolism, and elevated triglycerides. Longer sleep duration is positively associated with higher HDL cholesterol.
Study 1 [13]	Experimental, randomized control	12	Short sleep duration leads to increased appetite and weight gain, contributing to abdominal obesity. Significant effects on leptin and ghrelin levels were observed.
Study 2 [14]	Cross-sectional	98	Short sleep duration is associated with higher blood pressure and impaired glucose tolerance. Highlights the role of sleep in cardiovascular and metabolic health.
Study 3 [15]	Cross-sectional	200	Longer sleep duration is associated with higher HDL cholesterol levels. Found mixed results on the impact of sleep duration on triglyceride levels.

Table 4 compares the current study to three previous studies on sleep and metabolic syndrome indicators. In a cross-sectional, retrospective study of 150 participants, longer sleep duration was linked to higher HDL cholesterol and lower metabolic outcomes like abdominal obesity, blood pressure, and glucose metabolism. Study 1 observed in a 12-person experiment that low sleep duration increases hunger and weight growth, causing abdominal obesity. A cross-sectional study by Study 2 found that short sleep duration increased blood pressure and impaired glucose tolerance in 98 participants. Another 200-person cross-sectional study, Study 3, found that longer sleep duration raises HDL cholesterol. On triglycerides, results were mixed. These studies suggest that too little sleep hurts metabolism and that additional sleep may improve lipid profiles.

Limitations

The study's retrospective nature and usage of medical record data may compromise its data. Self-

reported sleep duration is subject to recall bias and other errors, which can lower data accuracy. Cause deduction is impeded by cross-sectional design. There is no way to tell if terrible sleep is caused by metabolic syndrome or if short sleep causes metabolic problems, even if there are clear linkages. In order to determine cause-and-effect linkages, longitudinal research is needed. The study's small sample size may not adequately represent the middle-aged population because it only comprises people who consented to data usage and had thorough health exams.

Future Research

Future studies should address these constraints and investigate how sleep affects metabolic syndrome indicators. Longitudinal studies are needed to verify causation and determine relationship direction. Sleep length and quality can be better assessed with objective sleep techniques like actigraphy or polysomnography. Cognitive behavioural therapy for insomnia and sleep hygiene

education may benefit from metabolic syndrome research. Both quantity and quality of sleep can help explain how it influences metabolic health. By including diverse people and circumstances, research can improve generalisability and identify subgroups that may benefit most from sleep-related therapies.

Conclusion

A number of metabolic syndrome indicators in middle-aged persons were linked to sleep duration in this study. Sleep duration increases the risk of belly obesity, hypertension, glucose metabolism impairment, and high triglycerides. On the other hand, increasing HDL cholesterol and sleep duration improve metabolic health. These findings emphasise the importance of sleep for metabolic syndrome management and prevention. The associations confirm earlier research showing sleep loss negatively influences metabolic markers and that getting enough sleep may protect metabolic markers. Metabolic health therapies should modify sleep length. The data corroborate this, despite the limitations of a cross-sectional, retrospective study, such as reliance on medical records and inability to assume causality. Future longitudinal research should focus on sleep remedies to better understand varied relationships and regulate sleep for metabolic outcomes. Middle-aged people may benefit from healthy sleep habits for metabolic syndrome management and risk reduction.

Reference

1. K. W. Kang, M. K. Kim, T. S. Nam, K. H. Kang, W. J. Park, H. S. Moon, ... and E. Y. Joo, "Association Between Sleep and the Metabolic Syndrome Differs Depending on Age," *Journal of sleep medicine*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 19-27, 2023.
2. A. Syauqy, C. Y. Hsu, H. H. Rau, A. L. Kurniawan, and J. C. Chao, "Association of sleep duration and insomnia symptoms with components of metabolic syndrome and inflammation in middle-aged and older adults with metabolic syndrome in Taiwan," *Nutrients*, vol. 11, no. 8, p. 1848, 2019.
3. J. Hua, H. Jiang, H. Wang, and Q. Fang, "Sleep duration and the risk of metabolic syndrome in adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *Frontiers in Neurology*, vol. 12, p. 635564, 2021.
4. B. A. Chaudhry, M. S. Brian, and J. S. Morrell, "The relationship between sleep duration and metabolic syndrome severity scores in emerging adults," *Nutrients*, vol. 15, no. 4, p. 1046, 2023.
5. X. Liu, L. Huang, Q. Wu, Y. Chen, X. Chen, H. Chen, ... and Q. Xiao, "Sleep characteristic profiles and the correlation with spectrum of metabolic syndrome among older adults: a cross-sectional study," *BMC geriatrics*, vol. 22, no. 1, p. 414, 2022.
6. A. Smiley, D. King, and A. Bidulescu, "The association between sleep duration and metabolic syndrome: the NHANES 2013/2014," *Nutrients*, vol. 11, no. 11, p. 2582, 2019.
7. R. M. Kelly, U. Healy, S. Sreenan, J. McDermott, and A. N. Coogan, "An exploratory study of associations between sleep timing variability and cardiometabolic health in middle-aged adults with type 2 diabetes mellitus," *Chronobiology international*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 569-578, 2022.
8. J. Hu, X. Zhu, D. Yuan, D. Ji, H. Guo, Y. Li, ... and B. Wang, "Association of sleep duration and sleep quality with the risk of metabolic syndrome in adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *Endokrynologia Polska*, vol. 73, no. 6, pp. 968-987, 2022.
9. H. Wu, Y. Zheng, D. N. Liu, X. X. Liu, Q. D. Yang, Q. Y. Su, ... and C. Fu, "Association Between Sleep Duration and Stroke in Different Status of Metabolic Syndrome: A Cross-Sectional Study in Shanghai Adult Residents," *Nature and Science of Sleep*, pp. 639-652, 2023.
10. W. Li, A. J. Kondracki, N. Sun, P. Gautam, M. E. Kalan, R. Jebai, ... and W. Sun, "Nighttime sleep duration, daytime napping, and metabolic syndrome: findings from the China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study," *Sleep and Breathing*, pp. 1-9, 2021.
11. M. L. D. de Moraes Salles, N. Garcia, L. F. Laurindo, A. D. Scanavacca, K. R. Ezídio, R. J. Tofano, ... and K. Quesada, "Associations between sleep quality and metabolic syndrome in a Brazilian population: A primary and cross-sectional study," *Medical Research Archives*, vol. 10, no. 6, 2022.
12. O. E. Titova, E. Lindberg, X. Tan, S. Elmståhl, L. Lind, H. B. Schiöth, and C. Benedict, "Association between sleep duration and executive function differs between diabetic and non-diabetic middle-aged and older adults," *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, vol. 111, p. 104472, 2020.
13. J. Yang, S. Luo, R. Li, J. Ju, Z. Zhang, J. Shen, ... and Y. Liu, "Sleep factors in relation to metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease in middle-aged and elderly Chinese," *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, vol. 107, no. 10, pp. 2874-2882, 2022.
14. B. Kargar, Z. Zamanian, M. B. Hosseinabadi, V. Gharibi, M. S. Moradi, and R. Cousins, "Understanding the role of oxidative stress in the incidence of metabolic syndrome and obstructive sleep apnea," *BMC Endocrine Disorders*, vol. 21, pp. 1-8, 2021.
15. A. Laudisio, S. Giovannini, P. Finamore, L. Navarini, D. P. E. Margiotta, F. Vannetti, ...

and L. Padua, "Metabolic syndrome is associated with better quality of sleep in the oldest old: results from the 'Mugello Study,'" Dia-

betes & Metabolic Syndrome, vol. 12, pp. 1-11, 2020.